

ISic0322

I.Sicily inscription 0322

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tom Gavin,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 445

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]ndri · v(ixit) · a(annis) · LX
2. [A]mabilis · nutrici
3. o(ptimae) · d(e) · s(e) · m(erenti)
4. [i]tem · Crescenti
5. v(ixit) · a(nnis) · XXV
6. [ea][d]em · Amabilis
7. [co]niugi · o(ptimo) · d(e) · s(e) · m(erenti)

Apparatus

Text from Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

[...]to [...]andris, she lived 40 years; Amabilis (made this) for the best wet-nurse for being deserving; likewise to Crescens, he lived 25 years; the same Amabilis (made this) for the best husband for being deserving.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491531

EDR 139548
EDCS 21900360

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7038 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650758>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione. Helsinki. At 54

Rizzo, F.P. 1989. La menzione del lavoro nelle epigrafi della Sicilia antica: per una storia della mentalità. *Seia*. Palermo. At 61 no.16

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